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СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович, Шодмонов Ахрорбек Акрамжон угли СТАБИЛЬНОСТИ ДЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИМПЛАНТОВ.....	6
2. Насретдинова Махзуна Тахсиновна, Хайитов Алишер Адхамович ВЫБОР ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА ПРИ ЛЕЧЕНИИ КИСТ ВЕРХНЕЧЕЛЮСТНОГО СИНУСА.....	9
3. Ибрагимова Феруза Икромовна, Гаффоров Суннатулло Амруллоевич КИМЁВИЙ САНОАТ ИШЧИЛАРИДА СТОМАТОЛОГИК КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИНИ КЛИНИК-ЛАБОРАТОР ТЕКШИРИШ УСУЛЛАРИ.....	13
4. Musurmanov Fazliddin Isamiddinovich, Pulatova Barno Juraxanovna METABOLIK SINDROM BILAN KESHAYOTGAN YUZ-JAG‘ SOHASI FLEGMONALARINING KLINIKO-IMMUNOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	18
5. Шайматова Азизахон Рустамбековна, Ахророва Малика Шавкатовна ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ РАСПРОСТРАНЁННОСТИ И ИНТЕНСИВНОСТИ КАРИЕСА ЗУБОВ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА В РАЗНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	22
6. Насретдинова Махзуна Тахсиновна, Нарзуллаев Илғор Дилмуродович, Бахронов Бекзод Шавкатович, Абдуманнобов Жалолиддин Голиб ўғли, Сулаймонова Мехринисо Музаффаровна ХАВФСИЗ ХУРУЖСИМОН ҲОЛАТИЙ БОШ АЙЛАНИШИНИ ТАШХИСЛАШ ВА ДАВОЛАШНИНГ САМАРАЛИ АЛГОРИТМИ.....	25
7. Усмонов Фарходжон Комилжонович, Хабилов Нигман Лукманович, Мун Татьяна Олеговна, Усмонов Комилжон Одилович ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ГИГИЕНИЧЕСКОГО И ПАРОДОНТОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СТАТУСА ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ОТЕЧЕСТВЕННОГО ИМПЛАНТАТА IMPLANT.UZ С БИОАКТИВНЫМ ПОКРЫТИЕМ: РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ИНДЕКСНОЙ ОЦЕНКИ.....	30
8. Xasanova Lola Emilovna, Rizayev Jasur Alimdjaniyovich, Madina Yunusxodjayeva Kamaliddinovna TEZ PROGRESSIV PARODONTIT BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA ALVEOLYAR JARAYONNING DESTRUKTIV O'ZGARISHLARINI O'RGANISH NATIJALARI.....	33
9. Камнева Нина Анатольевна, Камнева Ирина Анатольевна ОБЗОР ПО ПРИМЕНЕНИЮ ОЦЕНКИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОИЗВОЛЬНЫХ ЭМАЛЕВОГО МАТРИКСА ДЛЯ УСТРАНЕНИЯ ДЕФЕКТОВ БИФУРКАЦИИ НА НИЖНЕЙ ЧЕЛЮСТИ В ОБЛАСТИ МОЛЯРОВ.....	36
10. Fayziboev Pirmamat Normamatovich, Axrorova Malika Shavkatovna TISH KARIESI BILAN KASALLANGAN VA SOG‘LOM BOLALARNING OVQATLANISHINI BAHOLASH.....	39
11. Мун Татьяна Олеговна, Хабилов Нигман Лукманович, Усмонов Фарходжон Комилжонович ОПЫТ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ДЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИМПЛАНТАТОВ “IMPLANT.UZ” ДЛЯ ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ДЕФЕКТА НИЖНЕГО ЗУБНОГО РЯДА. (КЛИНИЧЕСКИЙ СЛУЧАЙ).....	43
12. Мун Татьяна Олеговна, Хабилов Нигман Лукманович, Усмонов Фарходжон Комилжонович ГЕМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ТОКСИЧНОСТИ ОТЕЧЕСТВЕННОГО ИМПЛАНТАТА “IMPLANT.UZ”.....	50
13. Nasretdinova Maxzuna Taxsinovna, Baxronov Bekzod Shavkatovich, Narzullaev Ig‘or Dilmurodovich, Uktamov Dierbek Shuxratovich, Ikromova Guli Nemat kizi KUNDALIK KLINIK AMALIYOTDA XAVFSIZ XURUJSIMON HOLATIY BOSH AYLANISHI QAYD ETILGAN BEMORLARNI TASHXISLASH VA DAVOLASH.....	53
14. Hamroev Sharof Shomahmadovich, Ibragimova Feruza Ikromovna KIMYO SANOA TI KORXONASI ISHCHI AYOLLARI STOMATOLOGIK SALOMATLIGI VA HAYOT SIFATI ORASIDAGI BOG‘LIQLIKNI ANIQLASH KO‘RSATKICHLARI.....	57
15. Абдюсупова Камола Мирвалиевна, Хайдаров Артур Михайлович, Мухамедкаримова Севара Рустамовна ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ МИКРОБНОЙ ОБСЕМЕНЁННОСТИ ПАРОДОНТАЛЬНЫХ КАРМАНОВ У БОЛЬНЫХ ПАРОДОНТИТОМ НА ФОНЕ ГЕПАТИТА С МЕТОДОМ ПЦР.....	63
16. Abdullaev Dilmurod Sharifovich, Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Abdullaev Sharif Yuldashevich ROLE OF CYTOKINE STATUS AND ORAL FLUID AND BLOOD ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS COMBINED WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE (literary review).....	68

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ROLE OF CYTOKINE STATUS AND ORAL FLUID AND BLOOD ANTIMICROBIAL PEPTIDES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS COMBINED WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE(literary review)<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7813250>**ANNOTATION**

Generalized periodontitis is not only a focus of chronic infection and a source of sensitization, but also the leading cause of tooth loss (especially in older age groups), leading to serious destructive consequences that disorganize the maxillary system. This fact can seriously affect the quality of human life, making the periodontal problem not only medical, but also social

Keywords: Generalized periodontitis, role of cytokine status, cardiovascular system, antimicrobial peptides, oral fluid

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РОЛЬ ЦИТОКИНОВОГО СТАТУСА И АНТИМИКРОБНЫХ ПЕПТИДОВ РОТОВОЙ ЖИДКОСТИ И КРОВИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ГЕНЕРАЛИЗОВАННОЙ ПАРОДОНТИТОМ СОЧЕТАННОЙ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЕМ КАРДИОВАСКУЛЯРНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ(литературный обзор)**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Генерализованный пародонтит – это не только очаг хронической инфекции и источник сенсибилизации организма, но также ведущая причина потери зубов (особенно в старших возрастных группах), приводящая к серьезным деструктивным последствиям, дезорганизующим зубочелюстной аппарат. Данный факт способен серьезным образом повлиять на качество жизни человека, делая пародонтологическую проблему не только медицинской, но и социальной.

Ключевые слова: Генерализованный пародонтит, роль цитокинового статуса, сердечно-сосудистая система, антимикробные пептиды, ротовая жидкость

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SURUNKALI UMUMIY PERIODONTIT BILAN BIRGALIKDA YURAK-QON TOMIR TIZIMI KASALLIGI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA SITOKIN HOLATI VA OG'IZ SUYUQLIGI VA QONNING MIKROBLARGA QARSHI PEPTIDLARINING TUTGAN O'RNI (adabiyotlar sharhi)

ANNOTATSIIYA

Umumiy periodontit nafaqat surunkali infektsiyaning markazi va tananing sensibilizatsiyasi manbai, balki tishlarning yo'qolishining asosiy sababidir (ayniqsa katta yosh guruhlarida), bu dentoalveolyar apparatni buzadigan jiddiy halokatli oqibatlariga olib keladi. Bu haqiqat insonning hayot sifatiga jiddiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin, bu nafaqat tibbiy, balki ijtimoiy periodontologik muammoni keltirib chiqaradi.

Kalit so'zlar: umumiy periodontit, sitokin holatining roli, yurak-qon tomir tizimi, mikroblarga qarshi peptidlar, og'iz suyuqligi

Introduction: The dental status of patients with concomitant systemic disease is reduced to either a general body response to the disease itself, or to the oral cavity as an open system that has triggered its development. Many examples are given that the role participants of the pathological process in the oral cavity are epithelial cells and nonspecific immunity, microflora and its metabolites, the protective systems of the oral cavity, whose markers reflect the emerging imbalance in the organs and systems of the body. In this case there is a "bouquet" of diseases, which requires a versatile examination and comprehensive treatment. Therefore, our review of the literature emphasized the need for a comprehensive dental and system-wide approach, the implementation of which, organizes the coordinated work between the signaling pathways of cellular metabolism and organ function. Integral organism consists of many functional systems interacting simultaneously and sequentially. Most diseases are united by a common mechanism in which their interpenetration and interaction is observed, and, therefore, nowadays, combined pathology is considered to be the rule rather than the exception [1]. The association of oral and cardiovascular diseases was stated by clinicians more than a hundred years ago. Modern clinical studies confirm the frequent association of inflammatory periodontal disease and cardiovascular disease [2, 3], but whether this association has a causal relationship remains uncertain [4, 5]. Of all causes of mortality in the population, both worldwide and in Uzbekistan, cardiovascular pathology occupies a leading position. The main causes of death in cardiovascular diseases are acute and chronic coronary heart disease (CHD), cerebrovascular disease and hypertension [6]. This determines the relevance of finding new approaches to the prevention and early detection of circulatory system diseases. Traditionally, the risk of cardiovascular disease is associated with lifestyle, genetic and environmental factors. Non-modifiable risk factors are distinguished, such as age, family history, and modifiable, which can be controlled, as dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension, smoking, diabetes, high body mass index in combination with low physical activity, psycho-emotional and social factors. In addition to factors associated with the long-term progression of atherosclerosis, there are "trigger factors" such as inflammation, a cascade of hemostasis disorders and thrombosis. These triggers can lead to atherosclerotic plaque rupture, thrombosis, vessel occlusion and acute clinical catastrophe - acute myocardial infarction or stroke [7]. Obviously, such common risk factors as age, smoking, alcohol abuse, education and socioeconomic status, male gender, diabetes mellitus and overweight or obesity are important both in cardiovascular pathology and in periodontal disease, which makes it difficult for clinicians to assess their relationships [4].

On the other hand, clinical practice data suggest that a significant number of cardiovascular disease cases develop in individuals without classical risk factors [8]. For example, the proportion of deaths from CHD occurring in people with cholesterol levels below the population average is about 40% [9]. One hypothesis is that the contribution of inflammation to cardiovascular disease risk is not sufficiently covered by existing prediction models. Inflammation may originate, for example, from periodontal infection, which can modulate the course of atherosclerosis in the vascular wall through its systemic effects [10].

Periodontal disease and tooth loss are recognized indicators of oral ill health. Population-based cohort studies with follow-up durations ranging from 5 to 57 years have shown an association of tooth loss, as the most indicative marker of long-term periodontal disease, with overall mortality and cardiovascular mortality regardless of race, age, risk factors, and socioeconomic status [3, 11, 12].

According to the INVEST (Oral Infections and Vascular Disease Epidemiology Study), tooth loss is associated with the prevalence of carotid plaque, than provides a potential pathway for association with clinical events

[13]. A meta-analysis by F. Cheng et al (2018), based on 17 cohort studies involving a total of 879084 participants, confirmed the association of tooth loss with increased risk of CHD and stroke. The analysis showed that loss of two teeth was associated with a 3% increased risk of CHD and stroke. [14]. An Australian study involving 172630 people with cardiovascular disease found a link between tooth loss and an increased risk of cardiovascular disease and all-cause mortality [3]. A Dutch study involving 60174 patients with periodontitis noted that periodontal pathology has an association with atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease after adjustment for other risk factors: age, gender, smoking, diabetes, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia and socioeconomic status [15]. The Nagahama Study, which included 8124 participants, showed a positive correlation between tooth loss and arterial stiffness as measured by the ankle brachial index after adjustment for age, sex, and other general risk factors [2]. The Scottish Health Survey, an observational study of 12,871 participants over eight years, after adjusting for socioeconomic status, lifestyle, smoking, and baseline health status, found that patients with a higher risk of cardiovascular death [12]. A. Holmlund et al (2017) observed 8999 patients with chronic periodontitis for 15.8 years in a prospective study. The authors convincingly demonstrated that tooth loss, rather than bleeding gums or the characteristic of periodontal pockets, is associated with the subsequent development of acute myocardial infarction [11]. The overall risk of cardiovascular disease associated with periodontal disease is most clearly found among those under 60 years of age. For example, a case-control data analysis from a Danish population showed an odds ratio of 6.6 (95% CI: 1.69; 25.6) for the association between periodontal disease and CHD among participants under 60 years of age, although no association was observed among participants over 60 years of age. In a Korean population example, a 25-fold increased risk of ischemic stroke has been reported in 4059-year-old patients with periodontal disease compared with a 2.5-fold increase among those aged 60-79 years. Epidemiological studies in recent years have demonstrated an association between chronic periodontitis and arterial hypertension (AH). The NHANES III study, which included nearly 12,000 middle-aged individuals, noted a positive correlation between systolic blood pressure (BP) and clinical signs of periodontitis (degree of gingival bleeding, pocket depth, tooth mobility) [18]. Based on the results of the Korea National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (KNHANES) of 1,560 adults in 2008-2010, Korean scientists concluded that people with poor oral hygiene had a higher prevalence of BP even before periodontal disease developed and suggested that oral hygiene was an independent risk indicator for BP [19]. In AH, the presence of periodontitis in patients is associated with an increased risk of target organ damage. So, according to E. Franek et al. (2010), patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and periodontitis more often have increased myocardial mass of the left ventricle against the background of increased central systolic BP. Analysis of the relationship between metabolic disorders and periodontal diseases attracts the attention of researchers. Obesity is considered as a recognized cardiovascular risk factor. Obese people have a 1.5-fold increased risk of cardiovascular disease (including CHD and cerebrovascular disease), and 10-15% of all cases of cardiovascular disease are associated with overweight and obesity [7]. R. T. Demmer et al. (2012) analyzed data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III) and showed that body mass index and insulin resistance positively correlate with the severity of periodontal bone resorption, which is modulated through proinflammatory cytokines. In a University of Illinois College of Dentistry review of 309 papers related to metabolic disorders and periodontitis, 26 studies were original and all found a positive association between periodontal disease and the metabolic syndrome. The literature discusses the relationship between dyslipidemia and chronic inflammatory periodontal disease. Thus, according to the results of a meta-analysis by R. Nepomuceno (2017), which included 19

publications, chronic periodontitis is associated with a decrease in high-density lipoproteins (HDL), increased concentrations of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and triglycerides [2]. This analysis confirms the validity of controlling the lipid profile in patients with periodontal disease. A. Blaizot et al. (2009), based on a meta-analysis of 215 studies published from 1989-2007, found that the risk of cardiovascular disease was 34% higher in patients with periodontal disease compared to those with intact periodontium (pooled relative risk was 1.34 (confidence interval 1.27 to 1.42). At the same time, the cardiovascular risk associated with LDL elevations greater than 150.5 mg/dL was 1.25 (confidence interval, 1.18 to 1.33). The authors propose to consider, by analogy with LDL cholesterol lowering to reduce the risk of CHD, the feasibility of periodontal screening as a cardiovascular prevention measure. The thickness of intima-media (IMT) of the carotid arteries was determined in numerous studies as an objective indicator of the connection between periodontal disease and atherosclerosis [1]. Data from a prospective ARIC study showed that carotid IMT was associated with the severity of periodontal disease. Although this correlation was not statistically significant, the ARIC study showed an association between periodontal disease and coronary artery calcification by computed tomography (relative risk 1.51; 95% CI 0.54-4.23) after 2-4 years of follow-up [2,7].

Noteworthy are the results of recent studies that the presence of periodontitis exacerbates the lesion of small cerebral vessels and increases the risk of lacunar stroke [10]. In addition, periodontitis is associated with Alzheimer's disease, the severity of dementia, and the acceleration of its manifestations. The authors propose to consider chronic periodontitis as a risk factor for the development of cerebrovascular diseases.

The results of few works on the relationship between chronic periodontitis and stable CHD are multidirectional. A.F. Eliseeva (2011) showed that in patients with CHD chronic periodontitis has higher clinical and microbiological activity in comparison with the same in patients without background pathology [8]. In contrast, C. S. Johansson et al. (2014) found no significant association between CHD and chronic periodontitis in an eight-year follow-up [9].

Literature data on the association of periodontal disease and acute myocardial infarction (AMI) are contradictory. A meta-analysis of 22 studies of 129630 patients with periodontal disease and myocardial infarction showed an apparent increased risk of AMI in patients with periodontitis [3]. S. Renvert et al. (2010) reported an association between chronic periodontitis and recurrent myocardial infarction [1]. It has been demonstrated that patients with AMI are more likely to have periodontitis, and indicators such as oral hygiene, depth of periodontal pockets, degree of resorption and bleeding, were significantly worse than in the control group represented by the patients' relatives. On the contrary, some authors attribute the detected changes in periodontal condition to a prolonged stay of AMI patients in the intensive care unit and anticoagulant treatment [13]. Q. Shi et al. (2016), analyzing data from 17 case-control studies that included 3456 patients with AMI and 3875 patients without it, showed that patients with AMI had worse periodontal status, which confirms the association of myocardial infarction and periodontitis [4]. At the same time, the authors recognize that, at present, there is insufficient evidence of a causal relationship between AMI and periodontitis and emphasize the relevance of further clinical studies to assess the effectiveness of inflammatory periodontal disease treatment to reduce the risk of AMI. In general, according to current views, poor oral health can be considered as a "risk marker" rather than an independent cause for cardiovascular disease [2]. According to the scientific statement of the American Heart Association, observational studies support an association between periodontal and cardiovascular disease with a level of evidence A (derived from multiple randomized clinical trials or meta-analyses), independent of other common risk factors. The evidence accumulated at this stage allows clinicians to recommend that patients with moderate to severe periodontal disease be informed of a possible increased cardiovascular risk and the need for cardiac screening [4]. Four major pathogenic mechanisms have been proposed that unite oral inflammation and the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, as follows: (1) low-level bacteremia, in which oral bacteria enter the bloodstream and

penetrate the arterial wall; (2) systemic inflammation, in which mediators are released from sites of oral inflammation into the bloodstream; (3) autoimmunity to host proteins, which results from the host's immune response to specific components of oral pathogens; (4) proatherogenic effects caused by specific bacterial toxins produced by oral pathogenic bacteria [4, 10]. It is increasingly said that in periodontitis, daily manipulations like tooth brushing as well as tooth extraction or endodontic interventions can lead to transient bacteremia [4, 5]. The epithelium of periodontal pockets can serve as an entrance gate, where lipopolysaccharides and other antigenic structures of periodontopathogenic bacteria not only cause local inflammatory reaction, but also get into the systemic bloodstream through the periodontal microvasculature. The cell-mediated immune response in the gingiva is a primer for the destruction of local periodontal tissues, contributing to the spread of microbes, bacterial endotoxins and various microbial antigens through the bloodstream [3,6].

The possible role of a number of microorganisms, including parodontopathogens (*Chlamydia pneumoniae*, *Helicobacter pylori*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Prevotella intermedia*) in atherogenesis is widely discussed [10]. Periodontopathogenic microorganisms can

directly penetrate the arterial wall and colonize atherosclerotic plaques [7]. Systemic invasion by periodontal pathogens or endotoxins can cause chronic systemic inflammation, infiltration of inflammatory cells into the endothelium of large arteries and proliferation of vascular smooth muscles, which are the main stages of atherogenesis [8].

The results of modern studies confirm the presence of periodontopathogenic microorganisms in atherosclerotic vascular plaque. Thus, V. I. Haraszthy et al. (2000) found periodontopathogens in 44% of atheromatous plaques obtained during carotid endarterectomy [39]. S. L. Marcelino et al. (2010) report that *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (*P. gingivalis*) is the most common bacterium contained in atheromas, its presence was found in 50% of atheroma samples obtained from patients with periodontitis [40]. *P. gingivalis* and its outer membrane vesicles contribute to the binding of LDL to macrophages and induce macrophages to change native LDL, which plays an important role in the formation of foam cells and pathogenesis of atherosclerosis. *P. gingivalis* has been shown to aggregate platelets and induce the expression of cell adhesion molecules. It also activates endothelial cells, triggers endotheliocyte apoptosis, smooth muscle cell proliferation and, therefore, impairs vasomotor function. F. Cairo et al (2004) could not detect periodontal bacteria in carotid plaque in a case-control study involving 52 patients with periodontitis who underwent carotid endarterectomy. It has been suggested that detected pathogens may be innocent observers of atherogenesis and that indicators of inflammatory response may serve as a more significant risk marker than detection of individual microorganisms [3,7]. Plaque bacteria contain many structural and secretory components that either directly damage periodontal tissues or stimulate the immune system of the macroorganism. Bacterial lipopolysaccharides (LPS) affect the immune response by binding to Toll-like receptor-4 (LPS from *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*) or Toll-like receptor-2 (LPS from *Porphyromonas gingivalis*). An immune response directed against the infection also leads to further tissue destruction [6].

After stimulation with bacteria and their components (LPS, peptidoglycans), proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1p, tumor necrosis factor- α , IL-6, interferon- γ , IL-12, IL-10), chemokines (MCP-5, MIP-1a), prostaglandin PGE2 and nitric oxide are produced in periodontal tissues. Proinflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1p, tumor necrosis factor- α , interferon- γ , induce the production of prostaglandins E2 and matrix metalloproteinases, molecules that contribute to the destruction of the extracellular matrix of gingival and periodontal ligament tissues, and resorption of alveolar bone [1, 4].

A number of studies demonstrate the presence of increased levels of circulating inflammatory mediators in patients with periodontal disease compared to healthy controls [42]. Elevated levels of many of these mediators are significant for vascular wall damage and are seen as potential links between para-

odontal infection and cardiovascular disease, either as markers of disease or as participants in inflammatory reactions in endothelial tissue and atheromatous lesions [1].

The discussion of the role of C-reactive protein (CRP) in the combined pathology of the cardiovascular system and periodontal disease deserves attention. CRP (an acute-phase reagent that is mainly produced in the liver in response to various inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-6) serves as a marker of systemic inflammation in various conditions. Elevated CRP in the blood of patients with periodontitis indicates that oral infections are potent inducers of systemic inflammation, which can increase inflammatory activity in existing atherosclerotic lesions, thereby increasing the risk of cardiovascular disease [4].

In severe periodontitis, proinflammatory cytokines induce alveolar bone resorption by increasing RANKL expression and thus affect osteoprotegerin (OPG) levels. Increased OPG levels as a surrogate for RANKL levels have been found to be closely associated with an increased risk of CHD [5]. It is possible that serum RANKL or OPG levels may serve as an indicator of the severity of inflammation present as a result of periodontitis and a marker of CHD risk.

The systemic inflammatory response that may accompany periodontitis appears to be a link between periodontal disease, atherosclerosis and its cardiovascular complications.

Autoimmune processes play an important role in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis. Accelerated atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases occurring at a young age are observed in a number of diseases whose genesis involves autoantibodies, such as rheumatoid arthritis,

systemic lupus erythematosus [6]. Among the many autoantigens proposed as potential targets for independent immune reactions in atherosclerosis, heat shock proteins (HSP) are of particular interest because autoreactivity to HSP has been observed in the gums of patients with periodontal disease [7]. *P. gingivalis* and other periodontopathogenic bacteria contain human HSP homologues. For example, elevated levels of antibodies and T-cells directed against *P. gingivalis* HSP60 have been demonstrated in atherosclerotic plaques and gingiva as well as in the serum of patients with atherosclerosis and periodontitis [8]. Some authors present the mechanism of inflammatory periodontal disease effect on atherogenesis as follows: Through periodontal pockets as reservoirs of pathogenic microorganisms, bacterial components (endotoxins) are released into the systemic bloodstream, which mediate through proinflammatory cytokines and other inflammatory mediators, produced by respondent cells, cause vascular endothelial alteration, hyperlipidemia and lipid infiltration of the vascular wall, as well as stimulate and maintain the inflammatory response, thus having a proatherogenic effect [1].

Conclusions: Thus, given the high prevalence of periodontitis and atherosclerosis, the social significance of cardiovascular pathology, the possibility of effective treatment of inflammatory periodontal disease as a potential risk marker for cardiovascular pathology, further analysis of the relationship between these diseases is highly relevant for the preservation of public health.

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ЖУРНАЛ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ И КРАНИОФАЦИАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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